

Women Identity : From Innateness to Performativity

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Abstract The discourse surrounding the identity of women has evolved significantly across historical epochs, reflecting broader philosophical and cultural shifts. From the ancient Greek notion that women possessed an innate, biologically determined identity to the medieval Christian view that framed women's roles as divinely ordained, the understanding of what constitutes women's identity has been deeply influenced by prevailing societal norms and intellectual currents. In the modern era, thinkers such as Mary Wollstonecraft challenged these deterministic views, advocating for women's education and intellectual development as central to their identity. Simone de Beauvoir further revolutionized this discourse by arguing that women's identity is not a fixed essence but a construct shaped by societal conditions. Judith Butler expanded on this by introducing the concept of gender performativity, suggesting that identity is a continuous enactment shaped by social norms rather than an innate characteristic. As a philosophical concept, identity itself encompasses questions about the nature of selfhood, the role of personal experiences, and the influence of societal structures. This paper traces the evolution of women's identity from notions of innateness to the modern understanding of performativity. By examining how identity has been historically constructed and contested, we can better understand the complex interplay between innate qualities and social influences in forming women's identities.

Keywords Gender Identity, Social Construct, Performativity, Cultural Norms, Gender Fluidity.

Introduction

Identity is a public phenomenon, manifesting through performance and construction, subject to interpretation by others. This construction unfolds within discourse and social behaviors, including our physical movements, spatial presence, attire, speech patterns, and other embodied practices. Significantly, identity is repositioned from the 'private' sphere of individual cognition and subjective experience to the 'public' domain of discourse and semiotic systems of meaning-making. In this view, identity emerges not as an intrinsic essence but as a dynamic and fluid construct continually shaped and reshaped through interactions within a social context. Many commentators, therefore, like Bourdieu in his theory of 'Habitus' and Bauman in his discussion of 'Liquid Modernity,' subverted the traditional understanding of innate identity. Identity is constructed, emphasizing the role of structure, language, power, and social practices in constructing what we perceive as identity. Michel Foucault illustrates how societal institutions and discourses shape our understanding of identity. Foucault, in 'History of Sexuality,' empathizes with the discourse of identity and argues that rather than being reflected in discourse, there is no such thing as an absolute self or fixed identity. It is actively, ongoingly, and dynamically subject to construction in discourse, "In Foucault's thought, subjectivity is constructed through historically and culturally changing practices. Identities are thus dynamic and contingent; they are constituted through historically inherited modes of behavior, through norms, rules, beliefs, and styles which are specific to our culture. Through his historical studies, Foucault demonstrates how the practices and beliefs that we consider necessary have varied throughout history and are thus actually contingent. By denying identity as a metaphysical essence" (Oksala, 1998, 42)

Objective of study This paper traces the evolution of women's identity from notions of innateness to the modern understanding of performativity.

Review of Literature Various literature have been review for this paper which have been discussed through out the paper.

Main Text

Moving to the notion of women's identity is very complex and includes various factors like social factors, historical contexts, cultural institutions, and individual experience. To understand this complex issue, we must examine its origins, tracing the warp and going through time. Our journey begins with an overview of the concept of women's identity and its historical context—a voyage that invites us to question assumptions, challenge norms, and appreciate the resilience of those who have shaped it.

The concept of woman as an essential subject has long served as a rallying point for many feminists who have leveraged this notion in their emancipatory endeavors. Historically, this essentialist view of womanhood has played a pivotal role in North American suffragist movements. Opponents of women's rights often grounded their arguments in perceived inherent qualities of women, such as their nature, bodily makeup, sensitivities, smaller brains, and tendencies towards hysteria. Paradoxically, suffragist advocates harnessed these very biological characteristics to argue for women's suffrage, asserting their right to vote based on their sensitivity and claimed natural moral authority, positioning these traits as virtues that ensure their inclusion in the political sphere.

In ancient civilizations, women's identity was often tightly associated with their roles as mothers, wives, caretakers, and the locus of childbearing. The prevailing narratives emphasized biological determinism—the idea that a woman's essence resided in her reproductive capacity and that they are subject to live under the four walls of the home. From the mythic figures of goddesses in texts like Homer's Iliad to the societal expectations placed upon mortal women, the contours of identity were etched by tradition and reinforced by religious texts.

In Greek mythology, the depiction of women and goddesses is predominantly negative and troublesome, in stark contrast to the portrayal of men, who are celebrated for their strength and praised for their heroic and marital exploits. This entrenched bias reflects an inherent sexism that permeates these ancient stories. Women in Greek mythology are often cast in roles that highlight their inferiority, manipulateness, and propensity to bring about the downfall of men. This negative portrayal is not merely a narrative device but a reflection of the societal norms and attitudes of the time. It corresponded directly with the oppressive treatment of women in ancient Greek society, where they were often subjected to forced seclusion, denied equal status, and viewed as subservient to men. The myths served to reinforce these social structures, perpetuating the idea that women were inherently problematic and needed to be controlled. This normalized sexism and ill-treatment with women in mythology thus both mirroring and perpetuating the real-world inequalities faced by women, embedding these discriminatory views deeply within the cultural consciousness of ancient Greece. Powell opines in this context,

“...although male gods regularly pursued mortal women, it was altogether shameful for a goddess to consort with a mortal man” (2015, p. 211).

In the context of identity, the portrayal of the goddesses in Homer's Iliad Aphrodite and Hera—illustrates the restrictive restriction on women by a patriarchal society. These goddesses fall into distinct categories: the 'virgin,' the 'dutiful wife,' and the 'whore,' with their identities defined by their sexual behavior with men. This classification reflects a male-centric society that confines women's identities to narrow roles. The Iliad revels in masculine glory by overpowering and subjugating women, whose identities are contingent upon Zeus, their lord, and master, thus telling the story of limited roles assigned to women in a patriarchal world. Aphrodite is supposed to have remarkable power over both men and women “...being the goddess of love, sexual desire, and erotic appeal” (Powell, 2015, p. 202). From the inception of philosophical inquiry, femaleness was symbolically linked to elements that reason allegedly abandoned—the enigmatic powers of earth goddesses and immersion in mysterious female forces. The early Greeks perceived women's ability to conceive as a direct connection to the fertility of nature. Aphrodite is perceived as a problematic woman, having her own lustful and emotional desires.

Aphrodite is even implicated in Helen's flight to Troy, inspiring her with an insatiable passion. Aphrodite is told by Zeus that,

“No, my child, not for you are the works of warfare. Rather concern yourself only with the lovely secrets of marriage, while all this shall be left to Athene and sudden Ares.” (Illiad, Book V. 428-30).

From the inception of philosophical inquiry, femaleness was symbolically linked to elements that reason allegedly abandoned—the enigmatic powers of earth goddesses and immersion in mysterious female forces. The early Greeks perceived women's ability to conceive as a direct connection to the fertility of nature. This symbolic association framed women as embodiments of natural cycles and mysterious powers, contrasting sharply with the rational and orderly world attributed to men. This view perpetuated the notion that women were intrinsically tied to the primal and irrational aspects of existence, which were seen as both powerful and potentially dangerous. Consequently, women's roles were often confined to domestic spheres and reproductive functions, reflecting a broader cultural and philosophical tendency to marginalize them in favor of a male-dominated paradigm that celebrated reason, warfare, and public life (Lloyd, 2002, 2).

The rigid and patriarchal constructs of women's identity in the ancient Greek period are mirrored and reinforced by the philosophical doctrines of prominent Greek thinkers such as Aristotle, Plato, and Pythagoras. They perpetuated the idea that woman was an innate quality, biologically and morally distinct from man, and inherently inferior.

Pythagoras, with his belief in the inherent dualities of the universe, categorized women as passive and men as active, further entrenching gender divisions. These philosophical perspectives underscored the deeply ingrained belief in the natural and immutable differences between men and women, reinforcing the idea that a woman's identity was predetermined by her biological sex and societal role. These symbolic associations lingered in later refinements of the concept and the ideals of reason; maleness remained associated with a clear, determinate mode of thought, and femaleness with the vague and indeterminate. In the Pythagorean table of opposites, formulated in the sixth century BC, femaleness was explicitly linked with the unbounded - the ambiguous, the indeterminate — as against the bounded - the precise and clearly determined (Lloyd, 2002, 3).

Aristotle, with his patriarchal mindset, further discussed these notions by arguing that women were naturally inferior to men, both physically and intellectually, and most suitable for assisting men and only for and therefore destined to fulfill supportive and subordinate roles within the family and society. These ancient perspectives laid the groundwork for enduring stereotypes and limited the scope of women's identities to their biological functions and domestic responsibilities. Beauvoir also gives references to Aristotle on women's inferiority in the second sex,

“The female is female by virtue of a certain lack of qualities,” Aristotle said. “We should regard women's nature as suffering from natural defectiveness.” And Saint Thomas in his turn decreed that woman was an “incomplete man,” an “incidental” being” (2010, 25).

In ‘The Generation of Animals,’ Aristotle distinguishes between male and female, asserting male superiority. He posits that males possess higher rationality and active principles, while females embody passive principles, contributing mainly through reproduction. Although Aristotle acknowledges women's functional importance in procreation and childbearing,

“They are distinguished in respect of their faculty, and this entails a certain function. Now for the exercise of all function instruments are needed, and the instruments for physical faculties are the parts of the body. Hence it is necessary that, for the purpose of copulation and procreation, certain parts should exist, parts that are different from each other, in respect of which the male will differ from the female....Now in the female this special part is what is called the uterus, and in the male the regions about the testes and the penis, so far as all the blooded animals are concerned: some of them have actual testes, some testicular passages” (GA, 716A-B).

Aristotle's view reinforced a gender hierarchy where men were seen as the primary actors and women as their necessary but secondary counterparts. Furthermore, Aristotle insisted that what a woman is as a rational being must be distinguished from what she represents through her bodily differences from men. This distinction underscored his belief that women's intellectual equality did not translate into social or functional equality. By emphasizing the symbolic significance of women's physical characteristics, Aristotle justified a societal structure where women's roles were limited and defined by their biology, perpetuating a system of gender inequality that persisted for centuries (Lloyd, 2002, 29).

This perspective highlights a significant tension in Aristotle's thought. While recognizing women's intellectual potential, he nonetheless justified their lesser status and restricted roles based on their physical differences. Which he believed dictated their capabilities and societal functions.

From the perspective of identity as a dynamic and socially constructed discourse, Augustine's view of women as innately subordinate to men appears limited and reductive. Augustine, a renowned Christian philosopher of the 4th century CE, like many thinkers of his time, subscribed to the notion that women's roles and identities were predetermined by their biological sex. This view aligns with the broader patriarchal framework that defined women's identities as fixed and innate in ancient and medieval societies, confining them to roles centered around their reproductive capacities and moral weaknesses. Augustine, like Aristotle, was not a supporter of women's equality and shared a misogynist outlook, yet he can be seen as slightly positive compared to Aristotle. Unlike Aristotle, who overtly asserted women's inferiority,

"Although the existence of the female sex is no corruption, but natural." He acknowledges the naturalness of the female sex, yet he also implies that women have an innate quality of being women and suggests their inferiority. Despite recognizing their natural existence, Augustine still maintains that women are inherently secondary to men" (Lloyd, 2002, 29).

Aquinas insists that intellectual nature—the image of God in its principal signification—is found equally in both men and women, existing in the mind "wherein there is no sexual distinction." This emphasizes that, on a spiritual and intellectual level, men and women are fundamentally equal as both reflect the divine image. However, in a secondary sense, Aquinas argues that this divine image is more fully represented in men than women. He asserts that "man is the beginning and end of woman; as God is the beginning and end of every creature," suggesting a hierarchical order in which man holds a primary role. According to Aquinas, this hierarchy is rooted in the creation narrative, where man was created first and woman was created for man, not the other way around. This view reflects a broader theological perspective that sees man as the principal figure in God's creation, with women occupying a supportive and complementary role. This framework reinforces traditional gender roles within the theological and social context, positioning men as the primary agents and women as secondary, despite their shared capacity for intellectual and spiritual reflection (Lloyd, 2002, 35).

The division of masculinity and femininity is seen as a natural outcome of how matter individualizes the general human form. This perspective suggests that men and women possess the same level of perfection within the human species, but this perfection manifests differently based on their subspecific types. Therefore, while both sexes contribute uniquely to the human experience, their contributions are seen as complementary rather than identical. This view aligns with traditional notions of gender roles, emphasizing a natural division of labor and capabilities between men and women.

"Masculinity and femininity result from this basic division. Woman's body, then, is feminine precisely because of the way designated matter has individualized the general form of the species. For this reason, we may say in reference to the human species that male and female are equally human but not equal humans. Men and women have the same level of specific perfection, but this perfection is divided among male and female subspecific types" (Hartel, 1996, p. 7).

Mary Daly in *The Church and the Second Sex* says that Thomas holds that women are naturally defective. She then states,

“Thomas, of course, shares the feeling that women as such are not quite human. However, leaving all questions of grace aside, there is indecision in his thought on the level of nature itself” (Hartel, 1996, p. 1).

The discourse surrounding women’s identity began to shift notably during the medieval period, particularly with the work of Christine de Pizan in her seminal text, ‘The Book of the City of Ladies’. Pizan transformed the metanarrative by recognizing women as rational beings capable of virtue and sound judgment. In this book, she challenges the prevailing misogynistic views by recognizing women as fully human, capable of reason, virtue, and intellectual achievement. Pizan constructs an allegorical city where women of exemplary character and accomplishment are celebrated, thereby asserting their rightful place in human history and society. Central to her argument are the virtues of reason, Rectitude, and Justice, which she attributes to women, emphasizing their intellectual and moral capacities.

However, despite Pizan’s groundbreaking work, her ideas brought about widespread change in the perception of women’s identity in a short time. The deeply entrenched beliefs about women’s inferiority and the notion that their roles were innately determined continued to dominate societal views. Women were still largely seen through the lens of biological determinism, and their intellectual and moral capabilities were frequently overshadowed by the prevailing patriarchal norms. Women’s identity remained tied to their perceived inherent qualities, often used to justify their subordination (1999).

In ‘Emile,’ Rousseau asserts that men and women are, and ought to be, unlike in constitution and temperament, and thus should receive different types of education. He argues that while nature teaches us that men and women should work together, each has its own share of the work, with distinct means and feelings that direct them. This perspective reflects a belief in the innateness of gender identity, suggesting that differences between men and women are fixed by nature and justify distinct societal roles and responsibilities. Rousseau maintains that women are made for specific roles and that their education should reflect their ‘peculiar destination,’ emphasizing their dependence on men for both desires and necessities, thereby reinforcing the notion of innate gender roles. (2005, 344)

The Enlightenment era ushered in new perspectives. Philosophers grappled with questions of reason, equality, and human rights. Mary Wollstonecraft’s ‘A Vindication of the Rights of Woman’ challenged prevailing notions of female inferiority, advocating for education and autonomy. Her words echoed across continents, igniting conversations about women’s place in society. Wollstonecraft argues that women’s supposed differences in temperament and character are not innate but are the result of their lack of education and the limitations imposed on them by society. She contends that such views perpetuate the subjugation of women by falsely attributing their perceived inferiority and dependency to innate differences. By advocating for equal education, she challenges the notion that women’s roles and identities are biologically predetermined, arguing instead that women can achieve the same intellectual and moral capacities as men when given the same opportunities (Marry, 1992, p. 199). Wollstonecraft’s treatise highlights her belief that the differences between men and women are largely constructed by the unequal opportunities and expectations placed upon them rather than resulting from their natural disposition.

This stance sets the stage for later feminist thinkers like Beauvoir, who would more explicitly articulate the idea that Gender identity is not an innate quality but a social construct. Beauvoir dissected the social construction of gender, exposing the power dynamics that shaped women’s lives. Her existentialist lens illuminated the complexities of identity formation. The idea of innate gender identity underwent a drastic change when Beauvoir posited her theory about the social construction of gender. This shift from essentialism to social constructionism marks a significant evolution in the discourse on women’s identity. Beauvoir, society, and culture play crucial roles in shaping an individual’s gender identity through norms, expectations, and roles assigned to each sex. Her seminal assertion captures the essence of this view, “One is not born, but rather becomes, a woman” (2010, 330).

In ‘The Second Sex,’ Simone de Beauvoir begins by examining the biological differences between the sexes, highlighting how these differences have been perceived and

interpreted throughout history. She delves into the ways that biology has often been used to justify and reinforce social inequalities between men and women. Beauvoir asserts that, while there are undeniable biological differences, the significance attributed to these differences is socially constructed. She emphasizes that these interpretations have historically placed women in a position of fragility and subordination. Beauvoir points out that, unlike other species, human society has amplified and exaggerated the biological distinctions between men and women, using them to define and confine women's roles and identities. This societal emphasis on women's biology has led to the perception of women as inherently weaker and more vulnerable, shaping their destinies in ways that limit their opportunities and reinforce their dependence on men. It is in this context that Beauvoir makes her poignant observation,

"Woman – the most individualized of females – seems to be the most fragile, most subject to this pain and danger, she who most dramatically fulfills the call of destiny and mostly differs from her male" (Beauvoir, 1993, p. 26).

This nuanced view acknowledges the biological aspects while emphasizing that the societal interpretation and amplification of these differences are what truly shape gender identity. Beauvoir differentiates between woman and female, stressing that these terms, although often used interchangeably, carry distinct meanings. Female refers to the biological aspects of sex, while 'woman' embodies the social and cultural significance assigned to being female. Woman is not simply a more polite term for a human with female reproductive parts; it is instead a term with fundamental social significance. This distinction underscores Beauvoir's claim that womanhood is shaped by societal norms, expectations, and roles rather than being an innate quality.

Butler, discussing this assertion, writes,

"...female' designates a fixed and self-identical set of natural corporeal facts (a presumption, by the way, which is seriously challenged by the continuum of chromosomal variations), and the term 'woman' designates a variety of modes through which those facts acquire cultural meaning" (1986, 36).

In the process of becoming a woman, initially, a woman must present herself; within the confines of her home and her everyday tasks, she simply dresses. However, she 'dresses up for social engagements or public outings.' This process of dressing upholds dual significance: it aims to project the woman's social status—her lifestyle, wealth, and the social class to which she belongs—while simultaneously solidifying feminine narcissism. It serves as both her uniform and her attire. For the woman who suffers from a lack of substantive activities, she perceives her dress as an expression of her being. Beauty treatments and dressing become forms of labor that enable her to assert control over her person, much like how housework allows her to claim ownership of her home. She thus believes that through these acts, she is actively choosing and re-creating her identity. This daily ritual of beautification and dressing transcends mere routine; it becomes a significant means through which she constructs and communicates her identity, bridging her private self with her public persona. This practice reflects her endeavor to find purpose and agency in a societal framework that often restricts her roles and opportunities. Through this lens, her efforts in personal adornment are not just about aesthetics but also about navigating and negotiating her place within the social hierarchy, asserting her presence and individuality in both private and public spheres (2010, 649 & 650).

Ultimately, Beauvoir's insights boil down to a human condition that specifically relates to women within society: that of social construction posing as an innate being. It is a distinctly existentialist realization that there is no essence of womanhood, no divine feminine, merely a series of ideas and constructs that, over centuries, have become ingrained and passed down from mother to daughter. What society has internalized as an idea of what women should be is not natural but defined by historical, social, and political contexts. Beauvoir's assertion that "in human society, nothing is natural and . . . woman, like much else, is a product elaborated by civilization" (Beauvoir, 1993, 725) highlights the profound influence of societal structures on the formation of gender identities. She emphasizes that what we consider to be the 'natural' attributes of women are, in fact, the result of cultural and social conditioning. This perspective invites a critical examination of the ways in which civilization shapes and defines gender roles, often perpetuating

stereotypes and limiting individual potential. Beauvoir's statement encourages a reevaluation of the assumptions surrounding gender, urging society to recognize and dismantle the artificial constructs that dictate women's lives. By understanding that gender is a product of civilization, we can begin to challenge and change the social norms that constrain and define individuals based on their sex.

Her ideas starkly contrast with the earlier notion that gender roles are biologically determined and fixed. By highlighting the role of civilization in shaping gender identity, Beauvoir sets the stage for later theorists like Butler, who expands on the idea of gender performativity. Butler argues that gender is not something one is but something one does—a series of acts and performances dictated by societal expectations. This perspective continues to challenge and deconstruct traditional notions of gender, emphasizing the fluidity and variability of gender identity beyond the constraints of biological determinism.

The concept of womanhood holds significant importance for feminists in various ways. The second wave of feminism played a crucial role in defining the term 'women.' This movement was not merely a revolution or a set of policies; it also profoundly influenced thinkers like Butler. This leads to the question of how feminists define the category of women. This category is inherently unstable and has been increasingly understood as a social construction rather than a fixed biological reality. In the 1970s, one way feminists might have defined womanhood was by considering those with the capacity for reproduction. This definition was crucial, especially in light of how government powers limited women's rights over their reproductive choices. However, as feminist thought evolved, it became clear that the notion of 'women' is not fixed but is constructed through social, cultural, and political contexts, challenging the idea of an essential, unchanging identity. Butler sees,

"Beauvoir as the thinker who opened the door to gender subversion, even if she did not go as far as her methodological and conceptual framework would allow" ([Butler 2006](#), 122).

When Butler wrote 'Gender Trouble', the prevailing view was that sex and gender were distinct entities. However, Butler challenged this notion, arguing that these concepts could be the same. Her perspective on gender diverges significantly from traditional views. Butler posits that both sex and gender are socially constructed. The distinctions typically made between sex and gender are artificial, suggesting that biological sex does not inherently determine gender. According to Butler,

"Sex is as culturally constructed as gender" and she concludes that if that is the case, then gender and sex are the same (Butler 1999, 10-11). She calls sex a cultural norm because sex is no longer treated as something that is determined by the body" (Butler 2011, xii).

The distinction between gender and sex is used to separate the sexed body from the gendered behavior of people. Butler says that the distinction between sex and gender is intended to show that biological sex does not determine gender.

"If sex and gender are radically distinct, then it does not follow that to be a given sex is to become a given gender; in other words, 'woman' need not be the cultural construction of the female body, and 'man' need not interpret male bodies" (Butler 1999, 142).

It offers a profound rethinking of gender identity. According to Butler, gender should not be seen as an innate or fixed characteristic from which behavior naturally arises. Instead, she proposes that gender is a performative construct, meaning it is created and sustained through repeated actions and societal norms.

"[Gender] in no way a stable identity or locus of agency from which various acts proceed; rather, it is an identity tenuously constituted in time – an identity institutionalized through a stylized repetition of acts" (Butler, 1998, 519).

These repeated acts are not the expression of a pre-existing identity but are themselves what constitute and maintain the perception of gender. In this sense, further, Butler clarifies,

“Gender is the mechanism by which notions of masculine and feminine are produced and naturalized, but gender might very well be the apparatus by which such terms are deconstructed and denaturalized” (2004, 40).

Butler’s work builds on the foundational ideas of existential and post-structuralist thinkers to challenge traditional notions of gender. She contends that gender is not a fixed attribute rooted in biology but a fluid and dynamic performance shaped by social and cultural contexts. Butler argues that our understanding of gender is deeply influenced by the repetitive actions and behaviors that society deems appropriate for different sexes. By drawing on the works of existentialist philosophers like Jean-Paul Sartre and post-structuralist theorists like Michel Foucault, Butler underscores the constructed nature of gender identity, illustrating how it is continuously produced and reproduced through social practices.

“Sartre’s notion of “a style of being” and Foucault’s “a stylistics of existence” both point to the idea that our identities are not innate or fixed, but rather are formed through the ways we present and conduct ourselves in the world. Butler extends this idea to gender, which she views as a “style of the flesh.” (1999, 177)

However, she emphasizes that these styles are not entirely self-created; they are influenced and constrained by historical and cultural contexts. The histories of these styles shape and limit what is possible regarding gender expression. For Butler, gender is a corporeal style—an act that is both intentional and performative. This means that while individuals may consciously choose how to express their gender, these expressions are also part of a larger social and cultural performance.

Katherine builds on Butler’s notion that gender is a performative construct. She suggests that the repeated performance of gender roles not only reinforces these roles but also makes them appear natural. The social agent, through continuous enactment of a particular gender identity, begins to internalize societal illusions and cultural assumptions about gender, perceiving them as inherent truths. This ongoing repetition and performance solidify the gender identity, making it seem stable and unchanging. In essence, the process of performing gender creates a feedback loop where the performance reinforces the identity, which in turn reinforces the performance, ultimately stabilizing and naturalizing the concept of gender within the social agent and the broader society (Katherine, 2016, 19).

Butler’s notion of gender performativity profoundly challenges traditional understandings of identity. She posits that identity, especially gender identity, is not something one is born with but something one becomes through the performance of gendered behaviors. This view shifts the focus from an essentialist perspective, which sees gender as a static attribute rooted in biology, to a dynamic perspective where gender is an active, ongoing construction. This idea underscores the importance of recognizing the historical and cultural influences on gender identity. It suggests that while there is room for individual agency in how one performs gender, these performances are always situated within a broader context of societal expectations and norms. This perspective aligns with the broader argument of this paper that gender identity is not innate but socially constructed.

Butler’s perspective challenges the traditional understanding of gender as a natural or biological essence, suggesting instead that it is a dynamic and ongoing process shaped by cultural and social practices. This view has significant implications for understanding the fluidity and variability of gender identities and the ways in which societal expectations and norms contribute to their formation and perpetuation. By emphasizing the performative nature of gender, Butler opens up possibilities for subverting and reimagining gender roles, offering a more inclusive and flexible framework for understanding identity.

Conclusion

The evolution of women’s identity from being seen as an innate quality to a socially constructed phenomenon is a journey marked by significant intellectual contributions. This paper has explored the shifting perceptions of gender identity through the works of key thinkers, including Aristotle, Augustine, Aquinas, Wollstonecraft, Simone de Beauvoir,

and Butler. Each of these figures has played a crucial role in either reinforcing or challenging the notion of fixed, biologically determined gender roles.

Historical perspectives on women's identity, as seen through the views of Aristotle, Augustine, and Aquinas, have long entrenched the idea of women's inferiority and their divinely ordained roles. Christine de Pizan's early challenges to these notions marked a significant shift, but broader societal views on women's identity remained largely unchanged for centuries. Rousseau's reinforcement of innate gender roles was met with Wollstonecraft's critique, laying the groundwork for future feminist thought.

Simone de Beauvoir's assertion that "one is not born, but rather becomes a woman" encapsulates her argument that gender identity is not an innate quality but a social construct. She challenged traditional notions by emphasizing that gender is shaped by societal norms, expectations, and roles assigned to each sex. Beauvoir's work deconstructs the societal constructs that have historically relegated women to the status of the "Other," opening the door for a more fluid and dynamic understanding of gender.

Building on Beauvoir's foundation, Butler introduced the concept of gender performativity, further challenging the idea of gender as an innate quality. Butler's assertion that gender is "in no way a stable identity or locus of agency from which various acts proceed; rather, it is an identity tenuously constituted in time – an identity institutionalized through a stylized repetition of acts" (Butler, 1998, 519) offers a profound rethinking of gender identity. For Butler, gender should not be seen as an innate or fixed characteristic from which behavior naturally arises. Instead, she proposes that gender is a performative construct, meaning it is created and sustained through repeated actions and societal norms.

Butler's work extends Beauvoir's ideas by emphasizing that both gender and sex are cultural norms rather than natural facts. This perspective challenges the binary understanding of gender and underscores the fluidity and variability of gender identity, suggesting that gender is not as stable as sex and that gender is socially constructed. Butler's reasoning consists of the idea that sex is socially constructed, just as gender is socially constructed. The distinction between gender and sex is used to separate the sexed body from the gendered behavior of people. As Butler states,

"If sex and gender are radically distinct, then it does not follow that to be a given sex is to become a given gender; in other words, 'woman' need not be the cultural construction of the female body, and 'man' need not interpret male bodies" (Butler 1999, 142)

Conclusion In conclusion, the journey from viewing women's identity as an innate quality to understanding it as a socially constructed phenomenon reveals the complex interplay between biology, culture, and society. Through the critical insights of thinkers like Beauvoir and Butler, we gain a deeper understanding of the dynamic and performative nature of gender identity. This perspective not only challenges traditional notions of fixed, biologically determined gender roles but also opens up possibilities for more inclusive and diverse representations of identity. As these acts are repeated and continually performed, the identity is reified, and the agent's gender is stabilized. This ongoing process highlights the importance of recognizing and deconstructing societal norms to allow for greater fluidity and individual agency in the expression of gender identity.

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